

METHODS OF TEACHING SCIENTIFIC TEXTS TRANSLATION

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Abstract

Learning to translate from one language to another is becoming one of the relevant elements of teaching a foreign language in a non-linguistic university. The article deals with some topical problems of the formation of translation competence, the identification and activation of the individual abilities of students, the methods of teaching the translation of scientific texts.

Key words

teaching translation, professional texts, specialized terminology translation, interpreter's competence, analyze the lexical and grammatical points.

Introduction:

The growth of information in all spheres of knowledge, production and scientific activity is caused by the rapid pace of the scientific and technological revolution. There is a sharp increase in the number of special terms, of which there are millions in every highly developed language, surpassing by many times the commonly understood vocabulary [58, 62]. Since language, like a living organism, is constantly changing, its social nature attracts the attention of philologists and specialists in various fields of activity. One can notice the germination of special terminology in the literary language, as a result, professional terminology turns into the main source of replenishment of the vocabulary of the general literary language, therefore, the interest of teachers in the methodology of teaching the translation of texts in the specialty and, accordingly, special terms is not accidental.

Main part:

Considering the methodology of teaching the translation of professional texts, we single out the prevailing denotative dynamism of information transfer in a non-specific field of activity for an ordinary person, in contrast to verbal communication in ordinary everyday situations. There are quite high requirements for teaching the practical skills of translating texts in the specialty and special terminology. The

training of future specialists to work with such texts is of particular relevance in the framework of strengthening the economic integration of the countries of Europe and the whole world. So, in technical universities, and they are usually called non-linguistic universities, students often offer such subjects of their choice as "Foreign language in the professional field" or "Foreign language of the specialty" [5,215]. As a result of studying the discipline, a specialist must master the following professional competencies: learn to communicate in oral and written forms in Uzbek or Russian and foreign languages to solve interpersonal and intercultural interaction, using basic common vocabulary and special terminology in a foreign language; master the skills of summarizing a professionally oriented text, preparing a presentation in a foreign language using special terminology, preparing a report in a foreign language in a specialty; use foreign language skills in professional activities, translate specialized literature from a foreign language; read, understand, analyze both educational texts in the specialty and professional texts in the original. The above subjects not only mean the modernization of language education in a non-linguistic university, but also actualizes a number of problems in the formation of translation competence among graduates of technical universities, since it plays a role in the formation of qualification knowledge and skills of future specialists.

The purpose of implementing a competent approach to the process of teaching the translation of texts in a specialty based on understanding the origin of terms is to create translation competence, which includes speech, sociolinguistic, pragmatic, cognitive, linguistic, sociocultural and informative competences. We include etymological competence in the order of linguistic competence, since this is an important condition for teaching the translation of texts in the specialty, which have a large number of special terms. Etymological competence is the ability of students and future specialists to translate using the acquired knowledge about the etymology of widely used terms and words, about their original meaning, origin and functional differences.

The next used method of teaching the translation of texts in the specialty, using the component of the origin of special terms, i.e. their etymology is a problem-activity approach, which takes into account that during the training sessions the student does not receive information "on a silver platter", but acquires knowledge himself, while the teacher plays the role of a mentor and assistant. An important role is played by the analytical thinking of the future specialist, who has basic knowledge in the professional field and should be able to determine the communicative and pragmatic tasks of a foreign source text. For a student, it is necessary to be able to correctly and reliably decompose the translated fragment

into its constituent elements; learn to summarize and analyze the information received; be able to identify translation fragments and special terms that relate to different fields of science and are different in style. The student must also learn to argue the conclusions based on the results of the translation and summarize the information after the analysis. [13,17] The analysis of the available methods and developments for the translation of special texts gives the right to determine that these texts are universal, i.e. they do not always emphasize the originality of the source text. The process of translation activity is decomposed into levels, depending on the guess, intuition, outlook of the student or future specialist.

The method of translation of specialized texts is used depending on the personality of the translator, on his individual capabilities, on his erudition and knowledge of his specialty. In accordance with modern methods of teaching the translation of texts in the specialty, we try to present translation as a two-way activity, in the form of a process of interaction between the text and the translator. When translating, not only two languages are compared, but also two cultures in the broadest sense of the word [23]. The lexical composition of scientific and technical texts is currently evolving very intensively. Therefore, when preparing students for the translation of articles in their specialty, one should start with the specifics of translating German terms related to the main specialty. The main feature of the vocabulary of any special texts is the use of a huge number of terms, which create difficulties in their translation. Students should be taught to find equivalent meanings of terms when working with special texts so that they can provide additional explanations to the recipient of information when there are intercultural inconsistencies. V.N. Komissarov notes that "learning to translate is closely related to the language training of students, depending on which there are two learning situations." If "in the first situation, students are fluent in both the original language and the target language", then teaching is reduced to the formation of translation competence, the development of translation skills, the ability to use language tools at different stages of interlingual communication [18,3518]. The situation that we face in the non-linguistic audience of technical universities is as follows: the learning process begins in conditions where students do not have sufficient knowledge of a foreign language.

In this case, the learning process is much more complicated and requires high competence and professionalism from the teacher. [8,157]. In order to teach students how to translate texts in the specialty, we start by introducing students to the introduction to the specialty, with comparative texts of the professional orientation of the two countries, with the system of professional terms. The

described features of modern German texts in the specialty and the methodology for translating them into Uzbek or Russian will help the teacher in solving the main task when teaching professional translation: “to highlight typical difficulties in the translated material that the translator has to overcome when translating many other texts, to demonstrate typical translation techniques and point out the peculiarities of their use in various cases, show how the general principles of translation are implemented in the translation of a given text” [22,133]. Further study of the features of scientific and technical texts will undoubtedly be useful for improving the teaching of professionally oriented translation, as well as in the practical work of professional translators with German texts in their specialty. In the process of learning, the teacher not only draws students' attention to the features of a professional text, but also suggests how to analyze the lexical and grammatical points that are found in specialty texts.

Conclusion:

When teaching students of non-linguistic universities the skills of working with texts in their specialty, it is necessary to use various situations that occur in the professional field. Students should be involved in solving a problem that a specialist may face in their future profession. We suggest using situations where students in groups can discuss, arguing their decision more often. Arguing in the course of the discussion, students will be able to use their knowledge in the field of special subjects and a foreign language. At the end of the group work, it is possible to offer an analysis of certain examples in the form of a written individual assignment that reflects the situation in professional documentation [7, 79]. Such methods make it possible to rationally use the limited study time intended for learning a foreign language, transferring the main part of the work of students in completing assignments to independent and extracurricular educational activities. In this case, a foreign language is used as a means of acquiring new knowledge, and the activity of performing creative tasks replenishes the vocabulary, expands linguistic skills and their use in various fields, namely, it makes it possible to solve all the tasks that are set in the professionally oriented foreign language training program. Therefore, the study of modern features of scientific and technical texts and the improvement of the methodology of teaching translation are of particular relevance for a teacher of professionally oriented translation.

REFERENCES:

1. Ahmadovna SM. National components in the structure of speech etiquette in English and Uzbek languages. *Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes*, 94–97. <https://scholar.google.com/scholar?cluster=755324714995079481&hl=en&inst=8697446408056752236&oi=scholar>
2. Buxorova MX, Mansurova GM, Eshmurodov UK. FORMATION OF STUDENTS COMMUNICATIVE ABILITIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*. 2021(2):152-4. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=en&user=73RuxO4AAAAJ&citation_for_view=73RuxO4AAAAJ:u-x6o8ySG0sC.
3. Buriyeva, N. D., & Buriyeva, N. G. (2021). Teaching listening comprehension in ESP classes. *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR)*, 10(3), 623-627. indianjournals.com/ijor.aspx?target=ijor:ajmr&volume=10&issue=3&article=100.
4. Burieva, N. G. (2022). National and cultural specifics of the verbalization of the concept «personality» in English and Uzbek. *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 04 (108), 687-689. <https://oaji.net/articles/2022/679-1654871061.pdf>
5. Burieva, N. G. (2019). EFFECTIVENESS OF ENGLISH FOR SPECIFIC PURPOSES. *Modern Science*, (8-2), 215-217. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=k9R_vugAAAAJ&citation_for_view=k9R_vugAAAAJ:UeHWp8X0CEIC.
6. Erkinovna, Y. F. (2021). Politeness and Culture. *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES*, 2, 82–86. Retrieved from <http://mrit.academiascience.org/index.php/mrit/article/view/96>
7. Ishankulova Nilufar Tashkentovna. (2022). Creative Writing in Teaching German. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 7, 49–53. <https://geniusjournals.org/index.php/erb/article/view/1016>.
8. Ishankulova Nilufar Tashkentovna. (2022). Differentiated Instruction in German Classes. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 7, 157–160. <https://geniusjournals.org/index.php/ejlat/article/view/1171>.
9. Ishankulova Nilufar Tashkentovna. (2023). PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE AS A KEY FACTOR OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING. *International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities*. Finland Academic

Research Science Publishers, 11(4), 1985–1993.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7881919>.

10. Ishankulova Nilufar Tashkentovna. (2023). TEACHING GERMAN GRAMMAR TO STUDENTS IN THE DIGITAL AGE. International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. Finland Academic Research Science Publishers, 11(4), 2228–2236. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7893487>.

11. Mansurova, G. M., Eshonkulova, N. T., & Eshmurodov, U. K. (2021). THE TRAGEDY OF “JULIUS CAESAR”. Социосфера, (1), 54-56. http://www.sociosfera.com/files/conference/2021/sociosfera_1-21.pdf#page=55.

12. Mansurova, G. M., & Fayzieva, K. A. (2020). GENERAL CRITERIA FOR THE EVALUATION CATEGORY. Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University, 2(8), 227-230. https://scholar.google.ru/scholar?hl=ru&as_sdt=0,5&cluster=12425234196252427892.

13. Mansurova Gulbahor Makhdievna. (2022). Teaching the Interpretation of a Literary Text in German Lessons. Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching, 6, 27–31. Retrieved from <https://www.geniusjournals.org/index.php/ejlat/article/view/803>.

14. Mansurova, Gulbahor and Fayzieva, Kamila (2019) "EVALUATION CATEGORY IN FOREIGN AND UZBEK LANGUAGES ACCORDING TO THEIR PRAGMATIC CHARACTERISTICS." Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University: Vol. 1: Iss. 2, Article 41. Available at: <https://uzjournals.edu.uz/namdu/vol1/iss2/41>.

15. Mansurova, G. M., Eshonkulova, N. T., & Eshmurodov, U. K. (2021). THE TRAGEDY OF “JULIUS CAESAR”. Социосфера, (1), 54-56. http://www.sociosfera.com/files/conference/2021/sociosfera_1-21.pdf#page=55.

16. Mansurova Gulbahor Makhdievna. (2023). METHODOLOGY OF MASTERING LISTENING AS A TYPE OF SPEECH AND LEARNING ACTIVITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION. International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. FARS Publishers, 11(2), 858–864. <http://farspublishers.org/index.php/ijessh/article/view/573/550>.

17. Makhdievna, M. G. . . (2023). A Method for Solving Situational Problems, or a Case Method in German Classes. Miasto Przyszłości, 32, 258–261. Retrieved from <http://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/1142>.

18. Mirkhaydarovna, J. S., Irkinovna, D. N., Abdimuminovna, C. S., Shamsievna, I. P., & Kholmamatovna, B. L. (2023). Intensive Methods of Improving Linguistic Competence in the Russian Language of Students of Non-Linguistic Higher Education Institutions in Uzbekistan. *Journal of Survey in Fisheries Sciences*, 10(2S), 3518-3528. <http://sifisheriessciences.com/journal/index.php/journal/article/view/1589>.

19. Khalilova O.A. FUNDAMENTALS OF LEXICOLOGY // Экономика и социум. 2021. №3-1 (82). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/fundamentals-of-lexicology> (дата обращения: 12.04.2023).

20. Khalilova Olima Akhatovna. (2022). Teaching Pronunciation Skills. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 5, 279-282. Retrieved from <https://zienjournals.com/index.php/tjm/article/view/888>.

21. Khalilova Olima Akhatovna, Obzorov Islom Ruzievich. Prospects of the energy system in Uzbekistan. *Int J Appl Res* 2020;6(5):306-307. <https://www.allresearchjournal.com/archives/?year=2020&vol=6&issue=5&part=E&ArticleId=6717>.

22. Khalilova Olima Akhatovna. (2023). CLT PLAY AN IMPORTANT ROLE TO LEARN LANGUAGE EFFECTIVELY. *World Bulletin of Management and Law*, 21, 133-136. Retrieved from <https://scholarexpress.net/index.php/wbml/article/view/2571>.

23. Khalilova OA. Organizational Aspects of Developing Innovative Methods in Teaching. *Eastern European Scientific Journal*. 2018 Apr 10(2). <http://journale.auris-verlag.de/index.php/EESJ/article/viewFile/891/965>.

24. Khalilova Olima Akhatovna. TECHNOLOGY IN LANGUAGE TEACHING. *ajps* [Internet]. 2022 Nov. 8 [cited 2023 Apr. 24];2(11):11-6. Available from: <https://theusajournals.com/index.php/ajps/article/view/460>.

25. Khujanovich, E. U. (2023). The Effectiveness of using Mobile Applications in Teaching a Foreign Language. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 32, 288-292. Retrieved from <http://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/1150>.

26. Hikmatovna, A. N., & Kobilova, N. S. (2021). Sociocultural aspects of "linguoculture" clothing" in English and Uzbek languages, *electronic journal of actual problems of modern science. education and training*, 18-21.

27.

https://scholar.google.com/scholar?cluster=3281129292436106770&hl=ru&as_sdt=2005&as_ylo=2023&as_yhi=2023.

28. KOBILOVA, N. Literary Psychology and the Principle of the Epic Image. JournalNX, 7(02), 306-309. <https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/342765-literary-psychology-and-the-principle-of-1cb9cf8a.pdf>.
29. Niyazova Yulduz Tashmuradovna. (2023). GAMIFICATION IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN A NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITY. International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. FARS Publishers, 11(2), 912-917. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7689661>.
30. Niyazova Yu. T. Comprehend simple grammatical errors and effective ways of teaching grammar / Yu. T. Niyazova // Міжнародний науковий журнал "Інтернаука" . - 2017. - № 5. - С. 43-44. - Режим доступу: http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/mnj_2017_5_12.
31. Niyazova, Y. (2022). BASIC PRINCIPLES OF LISTENING TECHNOLOGY. Scientific Collection «InterConf», (110), 93-98. Retrieved from <https://archive.interconf.center/index.php/conference-proceeding/article/view/455ю>
32. Shohsanam Yunusovna Tohirova. (2023). TOLERANCE AS A THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL ASPECT IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE. International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. Finland Academic Research Science Publishers, 11(6), 205-215. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8019206>.
33. Soliyeva Munavvar Akhmadovna Main components of organizing independent work of students // Достижения науки и образования. 2017. №4 (17). <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/main-components-of-organizing-independent-work-of-students>.
34. Soliyeva Munavvar Ahmadovna, Nurullayev Bahrom Komiljonovich Information-communication technologies and multimedia in foreign language classes // Достижения науки и образования. 2019. №6 (47). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/information-communication-technologies-and-multimedia-in-foreign-language-classes>.
35. Soliyeva Munavvar Akhmadovna, Tulaboyev Bekzod Zamon Ugli The role of the independent work of students in the educational process // Проблемы педагогики. 2018. №2 (34). <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/the-role-of-the-independent-work-of-students-in-the-educational-process>.
36. Solieva Munavvar Ahmadovna. (2021). LINGUOPRAGMATIC FEATURES OF SPEECH ACTS. Euro-Asia Conferences, 41-44. Retrieved from <http://papers.euroasiaconference.com/index.php/eac/article/view/529>.
-

37. Soliyeva Munavvar Akhmadovna, Murodov Bekhruzjon Teaching and learning English through information and communication technologies // Достижения науки и образования. 2017. №4 (17). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/teaching-and-learning-english-through-information-and-communication-technologies>.

38. Soliyeva Munavvar Ahmadovna The formation and development of professional-oriented listening in a technical Institute // Достижения науки и образования. 2019. №8-3 (49). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/the-formation-and-development-of-professional-oriented-listening-in-a-technical-institute>.

39. Saidov, X. (2023). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ СОКРАЩЕНИЙ И ИНИЦИАЛИЗМОВ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 27(27). извлечено от https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/8735.

40. Saidov, K. S. (2022). LANGUAGE EVOLUTION AND LANGUAGE ECONOMY. INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE «INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION», 1(4), 108–115. Retrieved from <http://academicsresearch.ru/index.php/iscitspe/article/view/1019>.

41. Saidov, K. (2022, August). TELESCOPIC WORDS IN MODERN ENGLISH. In INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS. (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 154-162). https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=ru&as_sdt=0,5&cluster=16168631530126395931.

42. Shohsanam Yunusovna Tohirova The rise in the status of women in the society and presentation of the gender factor of English phraseology // Science and Education. 2022. №4. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/the-rise-in-the-status-of-women-in-the-society-and-presentation-of-the-gender-factor-of-english-phraseology>.

43. Tohirova, S. Y. (2022). The rise in the status of women in the society and presentation of the gender factor of English phraseology. Science and Education, 3(4), 2088–2091. Retrieved from <https://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/3276>.

44. Yuldasheva Feruza Erkinovna. (2021). POLITENESS MARKERS IN SPOKENLANGUAGE. Euro-Asia Conferences, 37–40. Retrieved from <http://papers.euroasiaconference.com/index.php/eac/article/view/528>.

45. Yuldasheva Feruza Erkinovna. (2022). The Principle of Politeness in the English and Uzbek Languages. Eurasian Research Bulletin, 6, 65–70. Retrieved from
46. <https://www.geniusjournals.org/index.php/erb/article/view/799>.
47. Yuldasheva, F. E., & Gulomov, S. (2022, January). POLITENESS LANGUAGE PATTERNS IN REQUEST. In International journal of conference series on education and social sciences (Online) (Vol. 2, No. 1). <https://ijorces.org/index.php/ojs/article/view/152>.
48. YULDASHEVA, F. (2023). ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ ВЕЖЛИВОСТИ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ЛИНГВИСТИКЕ. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 31(31). https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/9211.
49. Yuldasheva, F. (2021). Issues in creating corpus for pedagogy. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 5(5). извлечено от https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/2589.
50. Юнусова Г. Ва бошкалар. Methods of teaching the uzbek language in higher education. Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government, 2021, Volume 27, Issue 2, Pages 5525-5532 10.47750/cibg.2021.27.02.559 https://www.cibgp.com/article_11080.html
51. Юнусова Г. The doctrine of Abdulqadir Giylani and qadiriya. ПУМ Engineering Journal. (Scopus) Published Online: 15December 2021 <https://www.nveo.org/index.php/journal/article/download/2661/2297/2699/>
52. Буриева, Н. Г. Approaches to teaching writing in English / Н. Г. Буриева. – Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. – 2017. – № 6 (140). – С. 411-413. – URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/140/39353/>
53. Буриева, Н. Г. Using songs and music in teaching English to young learners / Н. Г. Буриева. – Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. – 2017. – № 6 (140). – С. 413-415. – URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/140/39354/>.
54. Сайфуллаева Дилафруз Ахмадовна, Содикова Азиза Хайитовна, Солиева Мунаввар Ахмадовна РАЗВИТИЕ НАВЫКОВ САМОСТОЯТЕЛЬНОЙ И ТВОРЧЕСКОЙ РАБОТЫ СТУДЕНТОВ ПО ОБЩЕОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫМ ПРЕДМЕТАМ ПО НАПРАВЛЕНИЯМ БАКАЛАВРИАТА В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН // Вестник науки и образования. 2020. №19-2 (97). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/razvitie-navykov-samostoyatelnoy-i-tvorcheskoy-raboty-studentov-po-obscheobrazovatelnyim-predmetam-po-napravleniyam-bakalavriata->.

55. Солиева, М. (2021). ASSESSING THE KNOWLEDGE OF STUDENTS ON THE MOODLE PLATFORM. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 1(1). извлечено от https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/2547

56. Ишонкулова, Н. Т. Methodological analysis of the concept of teaching conditions in secondary schools and non-philological universities / Н. Т. Ишонкулова. – Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. – 2021. – № 15 (357). – С. 312-314. – URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/357/79915>.

57. Ишанкулова НТ. ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРНЫЕ КОНЦЕПТЫ В ОБУЧЕНИИ ИНОЯЗЫЧНОМУ ОБЩЕНИЮ НА СТАРШИХ КУРСАХ ЯЗЫКОВОГО ВУЗА. Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире. 2016(5-4):59-62. <https://elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=26643323>.

58. Нурмурадова, Ш. И. (2016). Формирование у студентов интереса к профессии учителя в процессе педагогической практики. Молодой ученый, (9), 1162-1163. <https://elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=25964478>.

59. Нурмурадова, Ш. И. (2016). Информационно-коммуникативные технологии в учебном процессе. Молодой ученый, (9), 1163-1164. <https://elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=25964479>.